

ThrombUS+ Study A Ultrasound Data Collection Manual

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About ThrombUS+

Deep vein thrombosis (DVT) is the formation of a blood clot within the deep veins, most commonly those of the lower limbs, causing obstruction of blood flow. In 50% of people with DVT, the clot eventually breaks off and travels to the lung to cause pulmonary embolism. Clinical assessment of DVT is notoriously unreliable because up to 2/3 of DVT episodes are clinically silent and patients are symptom free even when pulmonary embolism has developed. Early diagnosis of DVT is crucial and despite the progress made in ultrasound imaging and plethysmography techniques, there is a need for new methods to enable continuous monitoring DVT diagnosis at the point of care.

ThrombUS+ brings together an interdisciplinary team of industrial, technology, regulatory, social science and clinical trial experts to develop a novel wearable diagnostic device for point-of-care, operator free, continuous monitoring in patients with high DVT risk. The device will combine autonomous, AI driven DVT detection based on a novel wearable ultrasound hardware, impedance plethysmography and light reflection rheography for immediate detection of blood clot formation in the lower limb. Activity and other physiological measurements will be used to provide a continuous assessment of DVT risk and support DVT prevention via serious gaming. The aggregated data will drive an intelligence decision support unit that will provide accurate monitoring and alerts. Extended reality will be used to guide experts to design exercises and patients to use the device optimally.

ThrombUS+ is intended for use by postoperative patients in the ward, during long surgical operations, cancer patients or otherwise bedridden patients at home or in care units, and women during pregnancy and postpartum. ThrombUS+ will use big data sets for AI training collected in the project via 3 large scale clinical studies and will validate the outcome in the clinical setting via 1 early feasibility study and 1 multi-center clinical trial.

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Terms and Definitions

Term	Definition
AI	Artificial Intelligence
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
DICOM	Digital Imaging and Communications in Medicine

Executive Summary

ThrombUS+ Study A aims to collect and create a labelled ultrasound image data set containing ultrasound image series and video clips of patients that undergo routine ultrasound scans on lower limbs, because of suspected deep vein thrombosis. The data will be used to train an AI model within ThrombUS+ project to achieve automated detection of deep vein thrombosis on conventional ultrasound scans. This document describes in detail the steps to be followed to properly acquire the required ultrasound image series and videos.

Clinical Study A – Ultrasound Data Collection Manual

1. Introduction

The following is a set of instructions for the collection of the ultrasound images/videos during ThrombUS+ Clinical Study A. The instructions are addressed to the healthcare professional conventionally performing diagnostic ultrasound scans on patients suspected of having deep vein thrombosis of the lower limb.

The manual is also available online at <https://app.thrombus.eu/studies/a/>

2. Overall data collection guidelines

Conventional procedure followed on site

- Perform the conventional ultrasound diagnostic protocol for suspected deep vein thrombosis of the lower limb as you would irrespective of the ThrombUS+ Study A.
- Record your findings in the conventional report as indicated by the protocol followed in your site.

Additional data collection for ThrombUS+ Study A

For the purpose of ThrombUS+ Study A, and additionally to the conventional diagnosis report, also complete the following structured report:

<input type="checkbox"/> Right <input type="checkbox"/> Left			
Use one table for each lower extremity, if both are scanned.			
Venous system of the lower extremity	Check if assessed	Compressible* No/Partial/Yes	Thrombosis* No/Yes
Common femoral	<input type="checkbox"/>		
Femoral-saphenous junction	<input type="checkbox"/>		
Greater saphenous	<input type="checkbox"/>		
Deep femoral	<input type="checkbox"/>		
Proximal third femoral	<input type="checkbox"/>		
Middle third femoral	<input type="checkbox"/>		
Distal third femoral	<input type="checkbox"/>		
Popliteal	<input type="checkbox"/>		
Tibialis/Peroneals/Gastrocnemius	<input type="checkbox"/>		
Other pathological findings			
Finding	No/Yes/Not Assessed	Location (if relevant)	
Varicose plexus			
Perforating veins			
Subcutaneous oedema			
Baker's cyst			
Other (specify)			

* Required

Follow the steps below to collect ultrasound images or videos as detailed.

It is advisable to create a new Ultrasound Study to record the data below for the ThrombUS+ Study.

3. Ultrasound data collection steps

Patient positioning and overall data collection sites

The patient lies supine or in Semi-Fowler's position (on their back with the head and trunk raised to between 15 and 45 degrees), with no rotation of the pelvis. The head and shoulders should be raised to encourage distension of the leg veins. The legs may be tilted downwards from the head by at least 30 degrees. This helps to fill and distend the veins, making imaging easier.

In all scanning positions:

The probe should be perpendicular to the vein.

During compression ultrasound, the probe should be compressed until the pulsatile artery compresses slightly.

Data collection 1: Common femoral vein (CFV)

Place the transducer in the middle of a line that connects the pubis and the iliac spine, along the inguinal ligament, i.e. transversely to the common femoral vein and artery.

Perform a short exploratory scan around the point.

Locate a frame of **inadequate** diagnostic quality.

Save an image of inadequate diagnostic quality.

Move the transducer and locate a new frame of inadequate diagnostic quality.

Record a second image of inadequate diagnostic quality.

Locate the common femoral vein (CFV) and common femoral artery (CFA).

If during the conventional diagnostic exam, you have located a site of vein incompressibility or direct thrombus visualization in this area, choose this frame for collecting data.

Start video recording.

- Perform compression ultrasound

Stop video recording.

Total estimated duration: 5 sec

Collection site 1	Image of inadequate diagnostic quality	Compression video

Data collection 2: Great saphenous vein (GSV)

Slide the probe 1-2 cm down the patient’s leg to find where the great saphenous vein branches off of the CFV.

Perform a short exploratory scan around the point.

Locate a frame of **inadequate** diagnostic quality.

Save an image of inadequate diagnostic quality.

Move the transducer and locate a new frame of inadequate diagnostic quality.

Record a second image of inadequate diagnostic quality.

Locate the junction of the CFV with the Great Saphenous Vein (GSV of SV).

If during the conventional diagnostic exam, you have located a site of vein incompressibility or direct thrombus visualization in this area, choose this frame for collecting data.

Start video recording.

- Perform compression ultrasound

Stop video recording.

Total estimated duration: 5 sec

Collection site 2	Image of inadequate diagnostic quality	Compression video

Data collection 3: Femoral Vein (FV)

Slide the probe a few centimeters down the patient’s leg to find where the CFV branches into the deep femoral vein and (superficial) femoral vein.

Perform a short exploratory scan around the point.

Locate a frame of **inadequate** diagnostic quality.

Save an image of inadequate diagnostic quality.

Move the transducer and locate a new frame of inadequate diagnostic quality.

Record a second image of inadequate diagnostic quality.

Locate the femoral vein and artery distal to the bifurcation.

If during the conventional diagnostic exam, you have located a site of vein incompressibility or direct thrombus visualization in this area, choose this frame for collecting data.

Start video recording.

- Perform compression ultrasound

Stop video recording.

Total estimated duration: 5 sec

Collection site 3	Image of inadequate diagnostic quality	Compression video

Data collection 4: Femoral Vein (FV) – augmentation with color doppler ultrasound

Locate the femoral vein and artery distal to the bifurcation.
Switch to color doppler operation

Perform a short exploratory scan around the point.
Locate a frame of **inadequate** diagnostic quality.

Save an image of inadequate diagnostic quality.

Move the transducer and locate a new frame of inadequate diagnostic quality.

Record a second image of inadequate diagnostic quality.

Locate the femoral vein and artery distal to the bifurcation.

If during the conventional diagnostic exam you have located a site of vein incompressibility or direct thrombus visualization in this area, choose this frame for collecting data.

Start video recording.

- Perform color doppler ultrasound
- Squeeze the leg distal to where you are scanning (calf)

Stop video recording.

Total estimated duration: 5 sec

Collection site 4	Image of inadequate diagnostic quality	Color doppler video

Data collection 5: Popliteal Vein (PV)

Move the probe into the posterior crease of the knee and scan to find the popliteal vein.

Perform a short exploratory scan around the point.

Locate a frame of **inadequate** diagnostic quality.

Save an image of inadequate diagnostic quality.

Move the transducer and locate a new frame of inadequate diagnostic quality.

Record a second image of inadequate diagnostic quality.

Locate the popliteal vein.

If during the conventional diagnostic exam you have located a site of vein incompressibility or direct thrombus visualization in this area, choose this frame for collecting data.

Start video recording.

- Perform compression ultrasound

Stop video recording.

Total estimated duration: 5 sec

Collection site 5	Image of inadequate diagnostic quality	Compression video

Data collection 6 [OPTIONAL]:

Direct thrombus visualization or site where compression ultrasound shows pathology

If during the conventional diagnostic protocol, you happen to visualize a clot or locate a site where vein shows pathological incompressibility, locate this site and record image or compression video.

Total estimated duration: 3 sec

4. Synopsis

Data collection for Study A:

1. Short, structured report following the table provided (page 1 or in the Annex)
2. Point scanned:
 - 4 points scanned via compression ultrasound
 - 1 point scanned with colour doppler augmentation
 - [optional] point of direct clot visualization
3. Ultrasound data collected
 - 10 images of inadequate diagnostic quality
 - 4 video clips of compression ultrasound (~3 min each)
 - 1 video clip with colour doppler augmentation (~3 min)
 - [optional] image/video of direct clot visualization
4. Order of collected DICOM files*
 - 1 - Inadequate first image of common femoral vein (CFV) – Tag: CFVr – [L/R]
 - 2 - Inadequate second image of common femoral vein (CFV) - Tag: CFVr – [L/R]
 - 3 - Compression video of common femoral vein (CFV) - Tag: CFV – [L/R]
 - 4 - Inadequate first image of great saphenous vein (GSV) - Tag: GSVr – [L/R]
 - 5 - Inadequate second image of great saphenous vein (GSV) - Tag: GSVr – [L/R]
 - 6 - Compression video of great saphenous vein (GSV) - Tag: GSV – [L/R]
 - 7 - Inadequate first image of femoral vein (FV) - Tag: FVr – [L/R]
 - 8 - Inadequate second image of femoral vein (FV) - Tag: FVr – [L/R]
 - 9 - Compression video of femoral vein (FV) - Tag: FV – [L/R]
 - 10 - Inadequate first doppler image of femoral vein (FV) - Tag: FV-Dr – [L/R]
 - 11 - Inadequate second doppler image of femoral vein (FV) - Tag: FV-Dr – [L/R]
 - 12 - Color doppler video of femoral vein (FV) - Tag: FV-D – [L/R]
 - 13 - Inadequate first image of popliteal vein (PV) - Tag: PVr – [L/R]
 - 14 - Inadequate second image of popliteal vein (PV) - Tag: PVr – [L/R]
 - 15 - Compression video of popliteal vein (PV) - Tag: PV – [L/R]
 - 16 - [Optional] Image or compression video of a clot – OPT-[L/R]

* *In case of two leg scanning, you will first acquire the DICOM files for the left leg (L) followed by the files for the right leg (R).*

5. Notes

Imaging should be conducted at the highest clinically appropriate frequency, realizing that there is a trade-off between resolution and beam penetration. This should usually be at a frequency of 5 MHz or greater, with the occasional need for a lower-frequency transducer. In most cases, a linear or curved linear transducer is preferable, but sector scanners can be helpful for difficult patients.

The potential benefits and risks of each examination should be considered. The ALARA principle (As Low as Reasonably Achievable) should be observed for factors that affect the acoustical output and by considering transducer dwell time and total scanning time. Further details on ALARA may be found in the current AIUM publication Medical Ultra-sound Safety.

Transducer preparation, cleaning, and disinfection should follow manufacturer recommendations and be consistent with the AIUM Guidelines for Cleaning and Preparing External- and Internal-Use Ultrasound Transducers Between Patients, Safe Handling, and Use of Ultrasound Coupling Gel.

6. References

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ThrombUS+ Study A
Ultrasound Scanning Structured Report

Lower extremity scanned: Left <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No			
Venous system of the lower extremity	Check if assessed	Compressible* No/Partial/Yes	Thrombosis* No/Yes
Common femoral	..		
Femoral-saphenous junction	..		
Greater saphenous	..		
Deep femoral	..		
Proximal third femoral	..		
Middle third femoral	..		
Distal third femoral	..		
Popliteal	..		
Tibialis/Peroneals/Gastrocnemic	..		
Other pathological findings			
Finding	No/Yes/Not Assessed	Location (if relevant)	
Varicose plexus			
Perforating veins			
Subcutaneous oedema			
Baker's cyst			
Other (specify)			

* Required

Lower extremity scanned: Right <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No			
Venous system of the lower extremity	Check if assessed	Compressible* No/Partial/Yes	Thrombosis* No/Yes
Common femoral	..		
Femoral-saphenous junction	..		
Greater saphenous	..		
Deep femoral	..		
Proximal third femoral	..		
Middle third femoral	..		
Distal third femoral	..		
Popliteal	..		
Tibialis/Peroneals/Gastrocnemic	..		
Other pathological findings			
Finding	No/Yes/Not Assessed	Location (if relevant)	
Varicose plexus			
Perforating veins			
Subcutaneous oedema			
Baker's cyst			
Other (specify)			

* Required